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Temporality of Arctic transport infrastructure: bridging seasonal supply in Egvekinot, Chukotka

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ABSTRACT

This article explores local impacts from and responses to seasonal configurations of connectivity and disruptions in the functioning of transport infrastructure in the Russian Arctic. While paying due attention to *longue durée* – historical processes and modernization ideologies – in the shaping of infrastructure, communities, and social relations in the Russian Arctic, our main focus is on the cyclical, repetitive, and fleeting seasonal time. Building on social science and anthropological literature on temporality and seasonality of infrastructure and social life, we engage with the concepts of *rhythm* and *taskscape*. Drawing on qualitative ethnographic data collected in the coastal town and regional hub of Egvekinot in Chukotka Autonomous Okrug, Russia, we emphasize how transport infrastructures, which are subject to ongoing social and environmental changes, are perceived and used as highly seasonal and constantly evolving structures. Our case study shows how local residents and actors manage seasonal interruptions in chains of supply through future-oriented dwelling activities. We argue that different seasonal configurations of transport infrastructure serve to fill the gaps in supply chains and to ensure local mobility and provisioning throughout most of the year.

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Introduction

The Arctic is a vivid example of pronounced seasonal rhythms that one can hardly ignore; all organisms, including humans, must adjust to dramatic temperature fluctuations and other seasonal implications to survive (Schweitzer, 2024, pp. 171–172). Not surprisingly, seasonal subsistence has been a traditional topic for anthropologists of the Arctic (ibid.). Humans and non-humans adjust to Arctic seasonality and changes in the natural environment; and the built environment is also part of these year-round natural processes. The latter is even more true for Arctic urbanized and industrialized communities, where natural variations, human activities, and infrastructural rhythms are closely entangled with each other.

This article focuses on seasonality in the functioning of transport infrastructure in the coastal town of Egvekinot in Chukotka, one of Russia's Arctic regions. Despite the fact that the Russian Arctic in general, and Chukotka in particular, have been at the vanguard

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of industrial development (Schweitzer et al., 2017), their multimodal transport infrastructures function on a seasonal basis and complement each other to support mobility and supply of remote communities. Waterways (the Northern Sea Route and the rivers) serve to transport people and goods in the summer (navigation) season, while winter (ice) roads function only from late winter through spring. Even aviation and year-round roads in the Arctic are affected by natural conditions more dramatically than elsewhere: there are favourable and challenging seasons for flying and driving.

There is a growing body of literature exploring the relation between time and infrastructure at large (Anand et al., 2018; Carse & Kneas, 2019; Schwenkel, 2013; Ssorin-Chaikov, 2016). At the same time, the relation between seasonality and infrastructure has more rarely been the focus of social scientists. In other words, most researchers have focused on long-term temporal effects of infrastructural development, ruination processes, infrastructural legacies, and futurities (Dorondel & Şerban, 2019; Gupta, 2018; Harvey, 2018; Kovač & Ramella, 2023). Only a few have explored short-term temporal fluctuations and rhythms (Kuklina et al., 2019) or paid attention to the seasonality-dependent functioning of infrastructure (e.g. Müller, 2024; Rail, 2024). Our research contributes to this growing scholarship on fluctuations and disruptions of infrastructure by highlighting and exploring seasonal configurations of transportation systems that affect provisioning of the Arctic.

Seasonal variability in functioning of the Arctic transport infrastructure and its vulnerability to climate change processes have dramatic consequences for provisioning of remote communities. The supply of food, goods, fuels, and construction materials plays a crucial role in wellbeing, and often in the survival of Arctic residents in extreme environmental conditions. For example, the materiality of food items, namely their perishability, along with the temporal fluctuations of transport infrastructure operation, namely its irregularity and discontinuity throughout the year, necessitate complementary use of different infrastructures to ensure food security for local communities. While delivery of construction materials and household goods can be carried out on a less frequent basis, regular supply of fuels and lubricants is critical for mobility, communal services, and the overall energy security of the local communities.

This research builds on data collected in the port community of Egvekinot located in the east of the Russian Arctic coast. This Chukotkan town that emerged in Soviet times (1940s) experienced hardships during the post-Soviet transformation and is now anticipating the arrival of new infrastructure projects. It is the administrative centre of Iul'tinskii District and a transportation hub for neighbouring rural communities. It is connected to the regional capital of Anadyr' and small Indigenous villages of the region. The community has a relatively well-developed transport infrastructure that aims at ensuring mobility of goods and people throughout the year.

The contextualisation of this case study within the Russian Arctic allows us to explore transport infrastructures and supply patterns on a national level. The combination of maritime and riverine transport with ice roads, on the one hand, and insufficient aviation services and the lack of gravel roads and railroads, on the other, characterize the systems of mobility and supply in the Russian Arctic. Here, transport is also dependent on the decisions and funds of the federal or regional governments that are responsible for the construction and maintenance of infrastructure and transportation of passengers and goods. While the Russian state used to be the major actor defining configurations of transport infrastructure, local traders and buyers also have been gaining agency in shaping supply chains in the region.

Although many researchers have addressed the provisioning of Russian Arctic communities and the grass-root distribution of goods mentioning the seasonality of transport infrastructures and supply logistics (Agapov, 2023; Davydova & Davydov, 2022; Goncharov, 2024; Karaseva et al., 2023; Kuklina et al., 2022; Vasilieva, 2019; 2022; 2024), rarely have they engaged with seasonal fluctuations in transportation as the main object of their analysis. The article aims to close this gap and explore the impacts of natural seasons and other rhythms on the operation of the transport infrastructure and, thus, on supply and mobility that predetermine overall social dynamics and quality of life. We focus not on a particular type of infrastructure but on the entire transport system in the settlement of Egvekinot to analyse seasonal infrastructural complementarity, gaps, and disruptions. We argue that infrastructures in the Arctic, which are undergoing multiple social and environmental transformations, function and are being used and perceived as constantly changing and highly seasonal. Our overarching research questions are: How do seasonal rhythms, along with calendars and schedules, predetermine the functioning of transport infrastructure and shape the system of provisioning? Which local practices and skills help residents adapt to what we call ‘patchy deliveries’?

The theoretical part of this article draws in part on previous research conducted by Olga Povoroznyuk and other colleagues in the Russian Arctic on the role of infrastructure politics and legacies in national identity-building, modernization projects, and patterns and rhythms of mobility and supply (Povoroznyuk, 2022; Schweitzer & Povoroznyuk, 2022; Kuklina et al., 2019; Sancho-Reinoso et al., 2022). At the core of the article’s empirical part lies the data collected in Egvekinot by Elena Davydova. She visited the town every time she came to conduct ethnographic fieldwork in Chukotka. Between 2017 and 2024, she made five field trips with a total duration of one year, and spent about half of her field time in Egvekinot. Despite the patchiness (Günel & Watanabe, 2023) of her fieldwork, she had the opportunity to live in Egvekinot during different parts of the year and to witness the rhythmical (dis)appearance of food items on the shelves of local shops. Moreover, throughout the fieldwork, these recurring waves of supply became more or less expected and predictable for her. Like other local residents, she learned particular tactics for handling future disruptions. Through participant observation while doing her own shopping and travelling via transport infrastructures, attentive observation of the assortments available in local shops during the year, expert interviews with local entrepreneurs and storekeepers, and informal conversations with consumers, she learned about the food supply fluctuations and how local people live through these rhythms.

Theoretical framework

Temporality and politics of infrastructure

There is a body of literature that explores infrastructure as terrain for modernization and highlights its role in the articulation of different temporalities and modernities. For example, Brian Larkin defines infrastructure as ‘physical forms that shape the nature of a network, the speed and direction of its movement, its temporalities, and its vulnerability to breakdown’ and ‘comprise the architecture for circulation, literally providing the undergirding of modern societies’ (2013, p. 328). That is why, he argues, infrastructural services are so closely entangled with evolutionary thinking that embraces the concepts of modern society, progress, and the future (ibid., 332).

Hannah Appel and coauthors (2018) consider infrastructures to be ‘spatiotemporal projects that unfold over many different moments with uneven temporalities’ and are never a finished product (ibid., p. 17). From their perspective, infrastructure is important as a signifier of the aspirations for the future and modernity of a nation (ibid., p. 19). As an analytical tool, infrastructure can be productive for thinking across different scales, ‘from the planetary epoch to the most intimate acts of individuals and communities’ (ibid., p. 20).

Another recent strand of anthropological and social science literature on infrastructure emphasizes that infrastructures are not static but constantly evolve over time. Even if they can be sometimes ‘imagined by the public in static terms’ (Anand et al., 2018, p. 73), they are permanently being built, maintained, reconstructed, planned, or ruined (Carse & Kneas, 2019; Howe et al., 2016). Researchers have focused on these different stages in the life cycles of infrastructure projects, their temporalities and futurities, to explore ‘their spatial, technical, material, logistical, political, and social properties’ (Appel et al., 2018, p. 19). While doing so, they have paid attention to different timescales, spanning from those that exceed human lifespans to those that correlate with human everyday activities (ibid., p. 19).

As Povoroznyuk showed in her research with Vera Kuklina and Gertrude Saxinger (Kuklina et al., 2019) on the Baikal-Amur Mainline railroad in Siberia, with reference to Lefebvre’s ‘rhythmanalysis’ (Lefebvre, 2013), everyday infrastructural rhythms in contemporary societies are predetermined by calendars, schedules, and governmental regulations. The power of such socio-technical rhythms shapes the lives and activities of individuals and groups, making them conform to the timetables and schedules according to which infrastructure operates. The case study of the Baikal-Amur Mainline has shown that infrastructures shape the rhythms of life, social networks, and economic activities in the communities along the railroad to the same degree – if not more – than physical and natural forces.

Yet, the ‘seasonal variations’ – that is, broadly speaking, natural rhythms and fluctuations, have been recently once again becoming more central to anthropological treatments of infrastructure. For example, the concept of hydrosocial cycles and hydrosociality have been extensively used by social scientists studying maritime communities (Budds et al., 2014; Krause, 2017). More recently, Franz Krause and Mark Harris (2021) have argued that the social nature of water reservoirs shapes the rhythms of life in river deltas. In his article, Ashley Carse (2012) writes about ‘nature as infrastructure,’ demonstrating how water management infrastructure, environmental politics, and technopolitics come together to regulate natural processes in the watershed of the Panama Canal. All these case studies clearly demonstrate the complex nature of infrastructure as a fluctuating but also cyclical configuration of social, technological, and natural environments, actors, seasons, and rhythms.

This article addresses long-term processes of planning, anticipation, building, maintaining, and deterioration of (primarily transport) infrastructure objects and then focuses on short-term, namely seasonal, fluctuations in functioning of infrastructure. While we recognize the importance of historical processes and modernization ideologies in shaping infrastructure, communities, and social relations in the Russian Arctic, our ethnographic focus lies on seasonal time marked by repetition, cyclicity, and immediacy.

Seasonality and food supply

Social anthropologists have always paid attention to the seasonality of human behaviour. More than a century ago, Marcel Mauss published a prominent monograph that already

highlighted the entanglements of environmental and social phenomena and indicated that seasonal variabilities impact other rhythms of social life (Mauss, 2004). Moreover, as one of the most recent observations of this topic states, many classical ethnographical records at least implicitly discuss seasonality of subsistence activities, ritual life, or social organisation (Cveček & Horejs, 2024, pp. 10–12). The importance of this topic for Arctic researchers has been highlighted by Peter Schweitzer, who emphasised that Arctic traditional subsistence activities such as hunting, fishing, gathering, or reindeer herding are highly dependent on particular seasonal circumstances (2024, p. 172–173). As climate change proceeds, affecting seasonal availability of resources, new studies focusing on the impacts of global warming on seasons have started to appear (Herman-Mercer et al., 2019; McNeeley & Shulski, 2011). However, the built environment, including transport infrastructures, is overlooked in this research. While many researchers have mentioned the seasonality of transport infrastructures and supply logistics in the Arctic region (Agapov, 2023; Goncharov, 2024; Kuklina et al., 2022; Vasilieva, 2019), rarely have they engaged with seasonal fluctuations in transportation and food provisioning as the main object of their analysis.

We draw inspiration from the work of Marcel Mauss (2004), who examined how natural phenomena – such as seasonal cycles – shape various aspects of social life; in our case, this pertains to the social dynamics surrounding the functioning of transport infrastructures. We also follow an approach to seasons explicitly formulated by Franz Krause, seeing them as ‘interlocking rhythmical phenomena’ (2013, p. 25, 29) and building on the concept of rhythms as defined by Lefebvre (2013) and Ingold (1993). For example, although the distribution of industrial food through supply chains in the North is aimed to prevent seasonal disproportions in the availability of products (Schweitzer, 2024, p. 172), the assortment in local grocery stores in Egvekinot fluctuates rhythmically throughout the year in the context of multiple recurring phenomena (Krause, 2013, p. 24) and primarily ‘the seasonality of logistics in the north’ (Agapov, 2023, p. 419). Paraphrasing Franz Krause’s statement, ‘human life is not monotonous,’ we can say that the supply of foods and goods is not monotonous as well. Diverse breaks create temporal intervals of relational abundance and scarcity. This article explores how consumers and entrepreneurs live through and simultaneously shape these intervals themselves, each filled with anticipation of, and sometimes preparations for, future cargo deliveries or forthcoming shortages.

We approach transport infrastructures as material objects and social relations embedded in landscapes. Tim Ingold (1993) argues that the landscape, defined as the world as it is known to those who dwell therein, is the congealed form of the *taskscape*: the interactive product of a multitude of related activities and processes (ibid., pp. 156, 162). In other words, landscape is a product of continuous rhythmic actions and processes that constitute the *taskscape*. Both are fundamentally temporal and should be understood in terms of process and movement. They are mutually interrelated, and Ingold himself eventually even dissolves the distinction between them (ibid., pp. 161–164). They are just different perspectives of how people interact with the world around them.

In developing these ideas, we apply the term *foodscape*, which has been recently used in the literature across various disciplines. Simon Vonthron and others distinguish four approaches to the notion: spatial, behavioural, systematic, and social-cultural (Vonthron et al., 2020, p. 26). Our research contributes primarily to the body of literature that falls under the latter category and explores ‘food procurement practices to show that foodscapes are not only part of a spatial environment but are also socially shaped’ (ibid, 26). We define *foodscape* not as just the spatial distribution of food across spaces and institutional settings

(Roep & Wiskerke, 2013, p. 208), as ‘a marriage between food and landscape’ (Adema, 2009, p. 10), as sites for the merchandising and consumption of food (Winson, 2004, p. 299), or as a synonym of food environment (Lake et al., 2012, p. 1). Rather, engaging with the Ingold’s landscape/taskscape framework, we perceive it as both a landscape and a taskscape, specifically in relation to food. If the taskscape of social life is characterised by a variety of interweaving rhythmic cycles and repetitions, which in their resonances produce a perceivable form of the landscape (Krause, 2013, p. 28), foodscape is both the material and perceivable spread of food in time–space and the rhythmical continuity of food-related dwelling activities that continuously bring food landscapes into being. The notion of foodscape allows us to explore food supply in the studied community from both perspectives: from the standpoint of particular activities and tasks that people perform in order to have food eventually; and from the perspective of a variety of food items as material objects spread across the landscape.

Historical and geographical context

In order to understand the work of the present-day infrastructure in the Russian Arctic, one should look, at least briefly, into the Soviet history of modernization and urbanization in the region. The Soviet politics of ‘high modernism’ (Scott, 1998) rested on the combination of extreme forms of social and technological engineering, belief in progress, an ideology of ‘mastering Nature,’ and unrestrained state power. This politics, supported by the centralized investments in large-scale infrastructure projects and use of forced labour for their implementation, especially from the 1930s to the 1950s, has resulted in a massive infrastructural build up and population growth in the Soviet Arctic (Schweitzer et., 2017). Late Soviet megaprojects, demographic and socioeconomic programs contributed to further urbanization, internal colonization, and industrialization of the region (Povoroznyuk & Schweitzer, 2023).

The Northern Sea Route (NSR), an internal shipping corridor that constitutes the main extension of the Northeast Passage (NEP), has played a tremendous role for exploration, population, and industrial development of the Russian Arctic coast (Vasilieva & Gavrilova, 2023). In the 1930s, it gave rise to a number of small- to medium-scale port cities along its way and formed the backbone for transportation and supply of Arctic coastal communities. It also triggered the construction of a network of roads, railroads, and riverine routes that were to serve the purposes of exploration, colonization, and resource extraction in the Soviet Arctic. Modern transport infrastructure, combined with the preexisting networks of ice roads, tracks, and reindeer trails, and supported by large-scale state investments, formed the so-called system of ‘Northern supply.’ It functioned in coordination with the publicly introduced regulations and time schedules to ensure connectivity and provisioning of remote and seasonally accessible Arctic communities on a regular basis.

The dissolution of the Soviet Union resulted in the long-term socioeconomic and demographic decline of the Russian Arctic. Withdrawal of state subsidies to Arctic communities led to infrastructural ruination and abandonment, reconfiguration of connectivity, and curtailing of the northern supply program (Schweitzer & Povoroznyuk, 2022). Not surprisingly, the shirking of local economies, sky-rocketing consumption prices, and deteriorating social services and quality of life predetermined the massive population exodus from the Russian North in general (Heleniak, 1999) and from Chukotka in particular (Thompson, 2008). Remaining Arctic residents had to learn to adapt to the lack of state-

provided infrastructure services that were earlier taken for granted (Humphrey, 2003). While the NSR continued playing a central sustaining function for some regions (Durova, 2020), the Soviet centralized system of northern supply turned into a system of patchy deliveries. To compensate for the declining transportation infrastructure, people had to rely on their social networks and on new technologies and patterns of mobility (Vakhtin, 2017).

Yet, paradoxically, the post-Soviet infrastructural debris were discursively and ideologically turned into a foundation of the recent modernization programs launched by the government. The post-Soviet ruins became an embodiment of multiple – socialist, postsocialist, and Indigenous – modernities and materialization of the continuous process of (re-)colonization of the Arctic (Povoroznyuk, 2020; Ssorin-Chaikov, 2016). As the case of the Baikal-Amur Mainline shows, state efforts to re-boost or ‘modernize’ the large-scale infrastructure of the degrading railroad in East Siberia were saturated by the infrastructural politics of identity and emotion. Such politics has been aimed at the reconstruction of subjects loyal to the strengthening authoritarian regime rather than at investments in local socioeconomic development and improved mobility and supply in the North (Povoroznyuk, 2022).

Egvekinot is located along the Northern Sea Route and was one of the outposts for the exploration of northwestern Chukotka in the Soviet period. But it would not have been built in early Soviet times (the 1940s) if geologists had not found a tin and tungsten deposit two hundred kilometres away from the bay. Since Zaliv Kresta afforded the construction of a deep-water seaport (Figure 1), its western shore became the entry point for the development of the Iul'tinskoe deposit (*Iul'tinskoe mestorozhdenie*) and the district in general (Pereladov, 2020). The seaport and the road connecting it with the mine appeared to deliver minerals to the central parts of the USSR. Due to well-developed connectivity and logistics, the settlement and its population grew in Soviet times, reaching their peak in the late Soviet period, when the population was almost 5,500. At that time, predominantly newcomers from central parts of the country lived there. After the dissolution of the USSR, the closure of the mine, a high unemployment rate, inflation, and disruptions in supply resulted in a sharp decline in the number of residents. Food insecurity and even provisioning collapse

Figure 1 The view of Zaliv Kresta and Egvekinot. Photo by Elena Davydova .

that happened during this transition period was the most visible manifestation of the crises for local people (Gray, 2021). Now, Egvekinot has approximately 3,146 inhabitants (Egvekinot, 2019). The majority of the population is non-Indigenous (mostly Russians, but also Ukrainians, Belarusians, and Kalmyks). However, the number of Indigenous residents (Chukchi and Siberian Yupik) has recently been growing as the residents of remote ‘national villages’ (*natsional’nye sela*) move to Egvekinot in search of better living conditions. Soviet infrastructure still sustains the post-Soviet population of the town.

Food supply fluctuations and seasonality of transport infrastructures in Egvekinot

Nowadays, Egvekinot is an urban-type settlement located on the coast of Zaliv Kresta (Bay of the Cross), which is part of the Bering Sea. The popular geographical imagination of the NSR extending to Pevek in Chukotka (Gavrilova, 2023), in fact, does not include Egvekinot, however, the town remains a regional hub with a seaport, an airport, one year-round gravel road, and several winter roads. These infrastructures connect the settlement to small indigenous villages of the region, the capital of Chukotka (Anadyr’), and further to other parts of Russia (Moscow, Vladivostok, Yakutsk, Magadan, etc.). The relative year-round availability of infrastructures and seasonal complementarity of supply chains contribute to the mentioned above influx of the Indigenous population from nearby villages to Egvekinot. It is privileged to remain accessible throughout most of the year. While it is connected directly to the capital of Chukotka by air, water, and ground, small remote villages often experience significant isolation for much of the year. They do not have airports, which limits their access to aviation. Some of them are located inland, and others, since the dissolution of the Soviet Union, do not get goods and food by sea, even if located on the shore of the Arctic Ocean. Only barges loaded with coal approach such coastal settlements. These villages get most of their cargo from Egvekinot via winter roads. As a result, there is a dependency on one type of infrastructure, and any problems in the exploitation of winter roads leads to a catastrophic situation where people do not have access to basic products essential to sustain life.

On the contrary, Egvekinot is flexible in terms of accessibility and, consequently, more secure in relation to access to food and goods. People who moved to the regional centre from villages and who spoke with Davydova emphasised that they found the quality of life in Egvekinot to be much higher than in local hamlets due to the availability of products. ‘There, we completely starved to death’ (*Tam nas sovsem golodom zamorili*), said one woman who came originally from Nutepel’men. The local government interested in reducing the costs of supporting life in hard-to-reach villages promotes these population dynamics and suggests resettlement programmes from remote villages to Ozernyi.¹ Although food supply in Chukotka is organized by local entrepreneurs, a number of governmental programs provide subsidies to decrease the price of so-called ‘socially important products’ and partly cover transportation costs. There is a state-subsidized shop (*sotsial’nyi magazin*)² (Figure 2) in Iul’tinskii district that delivers goods to remote villages under a government contract. Still, the support is not enough. The assortments of local shops do not meet people’s nutritional needs. The prices are hardly or not at all affordable for many residents, even those in Egvekinot. The inhabitants of villages regularly experience severe food shortages in local stores. Further, we focus on the logistics of Egvekinot to explore the implications of seasonal complementarity of supply schemes in this transportation hub. Since

Figure 2. A branch of the state-subsidized trading company in Egvekinot. Photo by Elena Davydova.

food supply is especially dependent on the seasonal cycles of transport infrastructure, we pay particular attention to the delivery of food items.

Sea transportation

Shipping is the cheapest way to bring goods to Egvekinot, so most cargo comes to the settlement in summer and autumn on boats from Vladivostok. When water opens after the ice breaks up, the seaport captain issues an official order in accordance with hydro-meteorological conditions and ships arrive at the settlement. That is the crucial part of the year for supplying the community, and wellbeing in general rises. Gasoline, coal, construction materials, and goods are imported annually in summer. The well-managed delivery of food supplies in this period significantly impacts the food security of the settlement and nearby villages in the upcoming winter and spring. In a sense, the beginning of navigation marks the beginning of a ‘new year’ – an alternative time reckoning to an official annual calendar. For example, in February or March, local people may call the previous summer’s cargo ‘this year’s cargo’ (*zavoz etogo goda*). Just as with the real New Year’s holiday, the arrival of the first long-awaited ship is also celebrated by a festival. People go to the seaport and greet the ship’s crew, offering traditional Russian and Chukchi food. They also implement the Chukchi purification ritual of smudging the ship with smouldering herbs, and indigenous creative groups perform songs and dances (Otkrytie navigatsii, 2024).

Entrepreneurs bring relatively small shipments until October. They order goods in Vladivostok approximately once a month, focusing mostly on delivering fresh vegetables and fruits (*svezhesti*) as well as non-food cargo. The seasonality of the food, which ripened at a particular time of year influences the range of fruits and vegetables brought in during the summer navigation period. For example, strawberries were brought in in June, and watermelons in the late July. The bulk of the food that includes meat, seafood, cereals, pasta, flour, canned goods, frozen semi-finished products, frozen and ordinary fruits and vegetables,

butter, vegetable oil, dairy, sausages, cheeses, baby food, confectionery, nuts, dried fruits, chips, tea, coffee, cocoa, juices, mineral water, lemonades arrives on the so-called 'last ship' in October or sometimes November, depending on weather conditions. The purpose of this delay is to fill the warehouses of the shops with products as late as possible to be able to sell them relatively safely until next year's shipping season. Thus, seasonal affordability of infrastructures is attuned to the material qualities of food and official expiring standards. One entrepreneur explained that expiration dates have decreased compared to Soviet times, when most food items (excluding vegetables, fruits, and dairy) were good for at least a year. Today, according to standards, only frozen meat and fish can be stored for one year; most other processed products have a maximum shelf life of six months. This means that if the food supply happens in October, most food in local stores will already be expired by March.³ The owners of shops do their best to bring the majority of food items as late as possible to extend the official shelf life of food.

The navigation period, especially October to November, is the best time for consumers, as the assortment in the local shops is the cheapest and most diverse. People use the opportunity to stock their refrigerators and chest freezers as much as possible in anticipation of future rises in prices, which go high in winter and especially in spring. However, even during the shipping season, technological disruptions or weather conditions can affect supply rhythms, creating additional and sometimes unpredictable gaps and food shortages. Entrepreneurs recalled the cases of crane breakdowns that slowed down the unloading of ships and, as a consequence, led to the spoilage of some products. Once, a ship having left Vladivostok began to experience power outages. Vegetable and fruit containers that needed constant temperature maintenance were disconnected from electricity for about ten days. The warehouse manager of one of the local stores recalled: 'Everything started to get mouldy there. When we received this container, we managed to save very little.' Another year, the last ship froze in Anadyr' and could not make it to Egvekinot. Local entrepreneurs had to transport their goods by snow-swamp vehicles (*snegobolotokhody*), which local people call *TREKOLY*.⁴ Due to unexpected additional time costs, some of this food was spoiled as well. In the 1990s, there was even a case of a boat sinking with all its cargo.

Entrepreneurs also complained about the deficit of capacity on ships, especially the last one of the season. 'We all, on the same ship, from the same market, from the same bases, all on the same day bring all the fresh stuff,' said one of them ironically. As a result, traders may bring less than is needed for the community. The situation at Vladivostok trading bases also impacts food security in Egvekinot. One entrepreneur indicated an awful food deficit in 2022–23 because goods were insufficient in Vladivostok in the autumn of 2022. His explanation for it was the 'the special military operation'⁵ that 'directed all the trains in another direction,' as he put it. However, he mentioned that it is more or less a general problem: every autumn, certain food categories disappear in Vladivostok because of purchasing rush. He complained: 'Chukotka, Magadan, and Kamchatka are loading on last voyages in October, but Vladivostok is suffocating due to a shortage of goods.'

Even if events go smoothly, the first hints of the deficits appear a month after the 'last ship,' because some products expire within several weeks (fruits, berries, and dairy). It must be kept in mind that food items spend at least 10 days (sometimes more) in containers on ships while moving from Vladivostok to Egvekinot. By the end of the year, there is an urgent need for new supplies, especially in the context of the approaching New Year's holiday, which traditionally involves setting an abundant table in Russia. The gap in food

supply becomes visible and palpable. This is when local entrepreneurs switch to another, but also seasonal, type of transport infrastructure – winter roads.

Ice roads and aviation

Some traders bring cargo several times per month while others order food just a couple of times for the whole winter season. Usually, roads start functioning around the end of December and are open until May. As part of the route runs along the bay as well as many lakes and rivers in the tundra, the melting ice and high water make the road impassable and shifts in timing may happen, especially in the context of climate change and the more and more plausible late arrival of the winter season. Entrepreneurs place orders in Moscow or Vladivostok by phone, and planes deliver food items to Ugol'nye Kopi (the airport settlement near Anadyr'). Here, they end up at a so-called sorting centre (*sortirovochnyi tsentr*) – located at the airport warehouse for all arriving air shipments. The goods are then loaded into TREKOLs and transported along winter roads to Egvekinot. The food delivered by this route is more expensive than products brought by boats, because sea transportation is ten times cheaper than the combination of air and ice road transportation. Not surprisingly, price tags on vegetables and fruits often mention two categories of food for sale: 'navigation' and 'air.' The first one is cheaper, but not as fresh as the second.

The spread of TREKOLs (Figure 3) in the last decade has intensified winter delivery of food items. In comparison to tracked all-terrain vehicles, they consume less fuel, are cheaper, and have more affordable spare parts. These vehicles travel back and forth between Ugol'nye Kopi/Anadyr' and Egvekinot, located at a distance of about 320 kilometres, mostly bringing vegetables, fruits, dairy products, eggs, sausages, cheese, and canned food. The rhythms of these winter supplies are relatively predictable and affected by other fluctuating phenomena, such as the purchasing activity of local residents, changing weather, aircraft load, and multiple breakdowns that happen occasionally. 'This is North,' said one trader, emphasising the risky and unpredictable environment. Indeed, TREKOLs may break down on their way to Egvekinot. There were cases when off-road cars overturned

Figure 3. The TREKOL near a local shop. Photo by Elena Davydova.

and hit cargo. Sometimes, entrepreneurs place an order in Moscow, but the airline refuses to take it on board as the plane is overloaded. For example, Russian Post (Pochta Rossii) has priority for loading. In another negative scenario, cargo from Moscow gets stuck in a sorting centre because the weather is unsafe for driving, for example if heavy snowfall prevents deliveries. This airport warehouse has gained a notably poor reputation. As a local storekeeper put it: 'Food will either freeze or burn up there' (*tam ili pmerznet, ili sgorit*). She confirmed her words with a concrete story about when their cargo spent one week in a sorting centre, and they had to get rid of 'burned' tomatoes and greens. Consumers also noticed that when a TREKOL arrives, some foods are brought to a store, while others are immediately put near trash dumpsters.

The technical capabilities of concrete businesses also impact the frequency of winter supplies. For example, there is a company that owns its own TREKOLs and brings fresh food more regularly than those traders who have to coordinate their supplies with independent carriers. The Chukotkan governmental programmes supporting entrepreneurs and aiming to enhance food availability influence the arrival of food shipments. For example, Chukotka Autonomous Okrug subsidises the transportation of eggs produced in Anadyr' to Egvekinot in late winter and spring. Local traders combine the delivery of eggs with the delivery of other food items to save money on transportation. They attune temporally and spatially foods arriving from Moscow with eggs produced in Anadyr' to increase the efficiency of their businesses.

However, the percussive sounds of the winter food supply rhythm in Egvekinot are festival-related deliveries. If Nuer people, according to E. E. Evans-Pritchard, temporarily adjusted their ceremonies and rites to seasons when food was abundant (1940, p. 84), Chukotkan traders do the opposite: they aim to organise the abundance by the time of state-established festivals. Most of their efforts aspire to prevent the temporary overlap of the supply 'breaks' with the holidays, as these festivals are an opportunity for them to make money. Since the highest sales occur on the eve of major public holidays, entrepreneurs try to make deliveries in time for New Year's and Orthodox Christmas (December 31 and January 6), Men's Day (February 23), Women's Day (March 8), Easter (April-May), Labor Day (May 1), and Victory Day (May 9). 'Everybody wants to sell flowers on the eighth of March,' confessed one of them. When Elena lived in Egvekinot in the spring of 2023, there was information that winter roads were becoming dangerous to use by the end of April. Like many other residents, she asked the sellers if there would be more supplies, to which one of them replied: 'Well, they cannot escape bringing them for the holidays.' Indeed, at the beginning of May, the last TREKOLs of the season arrived with shipments. To some extent, drivers and entrepreneurs ignore climate change, which causes the early melting of roads. They take certain risks for business purposes.

Thus, the frequency of the arrival of TREKOLs and boats to Egvekinot is not metro-nomic. Rather, it is a rhythm intertwined with multiple changing phenomena (Krause, 2013, p. 28). Consumers are attentive to these partly unpredictable and partly anticipated rhythms. They pay attention to any vehicles and boats arriving at the settlement, monitor assortments of all local grocery stores, ask sellers about future planned cargo, follow local WhatsApp groups that post updated information about new shipments, and share information about new goods personally with their relatives and friends. Some people freeze vegetables to prevent future shortages. This helps them stock up on food before prices rise and certain categories disappear from store shelves. Entrepreneurs also use various manipulations affecting the material transformation of food in time. They

regularly organise sorting through vegetables and fruits in the warehouses. If the goods are starting to spoil, they process them – freeze grated carrots or chopped fruits, make compotes and jam from apples, and ferment cabbage. Besides, many store owners also have cafes or canteens where not-so-fresh food is sent for processing.

Off-seasonal transportation

From May, people tighten their belts, as goods can get to Egvekinot only by air until the seaport starts working. This is the most challenging period in terms of the availability of food, because roads are already melting, but shipping has not started yet. Only the gravel and concrete roads within the settlement, along with a section of the Iul'tinskaia road connecting Egvekinot and Amguema, are partially maintained and remain functional. While these roads support various forms of mobility – such as walking (Figure 4), fishing, hunting, or supply of the Amguema village – they are not helpful for a commercial food supply of Egvekinot. By June, most foods will have already been sold out or expired. Almost no fresh fruits and vegetables, unexpired dairy products, sausages, or cheese will be available in the stores. Certain basic types of food like butter, potatoes, carrots, cabbage, or pelmeni may disappear completely. People start craving vegetables and fruits. They call this period starvation time (*golodnoe vremia*). This is when frozen vegetable stocks come in handy more than ever. A local woman shared memories of eating a whole onion without even wincing when the first cargo arrived.

Nowadays, some traders deliver cargo in small batches using small Canadian planes or helicopters flying the route Anadyr'–Egvekinot. But this cannot help to solve the problem of shortages. First, this is the most expensive food, as it is a double air cargo: it is brought to Ugol'nye Kopi by plane and then to Egvekinot by aircraft as well. Most people cannot afford it. Second, buyers who can afford it sweep away small shipments in a few days or even hours. The point is that entrepreneurs regulate the amount of food delivered throughout the year. The size of shipments correlates with a certain time of the year. As a general rule, the more expensive the transportation, the smaller the cargo. Traders are cautious of bringing too much food by air, as they can lose a lot of money on transportation expenses if they end up with a significant amount of unsold surplus goods. They balance preventing possible food shortages and maintaining a sense of light scarcity among buyers. In this regard, the largest consignments of goods are brought in by ships, and the smallest ones are brought in by small planes during the spring and early summer. Most entrepreneurs refuse to deliver food to Egvekinot by air as it is too risky: if the cargo is damaged or buyers do not buy it up, the business owner will lose enormous amounts of money spent on expensive transportation of goods. In 2023, for example, only one businesswoman brought food shipments in May and June.

Not surprisingly, since spring, people look forward to new cargo, discussing weather and ice conditions in the bay, and making assumptions about when navigation might start (Figure 4). As Karaseva and others pointed out, 'in the Arctic, the possible delivery periods ... fluctuate from year to year' (Karaseva et al., 2023, p. 132). In Egvekinot, since ice thawing varies yearly and is affected by climate change, navigation time is not tied to specific calendar dates as well. The current situation contrasts with the pre-existing late Soviet system. Then, there were widespread modernist concepts of human dominance over nature (Schweitzer et al., 2017, p. 64), and icebreakers were supposed to tame seasonal rhythms. Many informants recalled that regardless of the state of the ice, icebreakers would break

Figure 4. The embankment at the Zaliv Kresta in June 2023. The bay is still covered with ice, a sign of late navigation. Photo by Elena Davydova.

it open to pave the way for the first ships as early as May. Today, people reminisce with nostalgia about Soviet supply logistics that, according to their recollection, were less dependent on environmental processes due to ice breakers, had more available aviation, and had a much better developed network of winter roads compared to the current situation. Paradoxically, although natural global warming phenomena extend the time of open waters and are favourable for prolonged navigation, in reality, post-Soviet technological constraints and socioeconomic transformations shorten the shipping period, making people feel less secure. Not surprisingly, many NSR communities reproduce nostalgic discourses about Soviet-time prosperity and abundance of food and other material items that were delivered to them ‘directly’ from Moscow and were not available ‘on the mainland’. This idealized exceptional mode of provisioning that helped people to construct ‘an intimate relation’ between a periphery and the centre (Gavrilova, 2023, p. 377) was undermined in the post-Soviet period.

Discussion and conclusion

Transport infrastructures are ever-changing projects that unfold across space and time (Appel et al., 2018). In Chukotka, the functioning of transport infrastructures has evolved temporally as well. For example, financial and technological constraints of the post-Soviet period led to the collapse of the northwestern marine supply model based on the Northern Sea Route and a decline in the extensive use of aviation. In addition to socioeconomic transformations, climate change has long-lasting impacts on mobility patterns, notably disrupting the functioning of winter roads, while emerging modes of transportation, such as TREKOLs, create new opportunities for local mobilities.

Our research follows scholarship that has criticized the opposition between natural and built environments (Carse, 2012; Rippa, 2024; Schweitzer et al., 2017) and revealed how infrastructure frequently shapes the relationship between humans and their environment (Dorondel, 2016). As we have shown in the previous sections, alongside various long-term social, technological and environmental changes and calendars, short-term (mostly

seasonal) cyclical fluctuations in the functioning of transport infrastructure impact supply patterns. Systems of provisioning are embedded in the seasonal complementarity of local transport infrastructure. Seasonal phenomena such as ice conditions, snow cover, or snowfalls, along with the technological capabilities of (post)-Soviet infrastructure and modern transport facilities, all shape chains and patterns of supply. The delivery of food is particularly vulnerable to their fluctuations, as the materiality of foods changes more rapidly than that of other commodities.

The logistics of Egvekinot may seem rather smooth, especially compared to other more remote and isolated settlements of the Russian Arctic. More than other settlements, the town is connected with the main regional hub – Anadyr'/Ugol'nye Kopi – as well as with Vladivostok and Moscow. Due to the abundant Soviet infrastructural legacy that allows temporal complementarity of different types of transport infrastructure, Egvekinot is accessible by different types of transport for most of the year. People call this place 'Chukotkan Sochi,' stressing not only the maritime air and stunning mountainous natural landscape but its comfort in living caused by the relative efficiency of infrastructural services. It makes Egvekinot attractive for migrants from Chukotka's rural communities.

Nevertheless, infrastructural disruptions in the gap seasons, when supplies to the settlement are uncertain, challenges the perception of Egvekinot as an attractive and prosperous community. As we showed, supply logistics in this regional hub are far from smooth-functioning. From the point of view of its inhabitants, the complementarity of local infrastructures is rather discontinuous and requires effort to manage breaks and disruptions. The 'breaks' are not just a metaphor for the seasonal functioning of infrastructure but sometimes rather literal things. They can be real snowfalls, electricity disconnections, or vehicle breakdowns that materially break supply chains and create additional gaps in food availability.

Thus, in the post-Soviet period, the Russian state has withdrawn significant part of its financial support and lifted regulations that used to ensure smoother functioning of the system of provisioning of Arctic communities. Ordinary people (consumers) and traders deal with infrastructural disruptions that lead to 'patchy deliveries' through future-oriented activities, such as stocking up or processing of food items, to smooth or prevent anticipated disruptions. Businesses follow the logic of efficiency, since entrepreneurial economic activity must generate income. Although many locals have severely criticised some traders, accusing them of making excessive profits, this article refrains from making such moral judgments (at least due to the scarcity of facts for making the claims). The general point here is that the anticipation of future cargo arrival as well as deficits permeates local food-related practices. In pursuit of efficiency, sometimes morally justified and sometimes not, entrepreneurs creatively attune to the lifecycles of food products and to the seasonal rhythms of existing infrastructure. Buyers are no less creative and try to be efficient within their households. Both aim to smooth the fluctuations of supply and are attentive to 'seasonal variations' (Mauss, 2004) with their specific gaps and breakdowns. Based on their embodied knowledge gained through past experiences, they create strategies that help them handle anticipated future disruptions.

Supporting the idea that the rhythms of many social and ecological phenomena interweave (Ingold, 1993; Krause, 2013; Kuklina et al., 2019), we argue that they shape the availability of different food items at a certain time and in a certain place. Weather patterns, consumer demand, traders' annual purchases, carriers' work schedules, a series of national holidays, technological capabilities, and governmental regulations and programmes contribute to how food distribution is patterned in space and time. However, foodscapes are

inherently seasonal, as supply fluctuations follow a dominant seasonal rhythm that either enables or restricts the use of specific infrastructures and transportation methods for delivering food to the community.

Just as the landscape and taskscape are temporal, so is the foodscape. At ‘any particular moment, you can ask ... what it is like?’ (Ingold, 1993, p. 154), and with the passage of time, the forms that foodscapes take arise and change. For example, in December and June, the foodscapes in Egvekinot are completely different. These differences are well known to dwellers who live through these seasonal foodscapes (Ibid, p.156). Foodscape has no boundaries, just like landscape and taskscape. Diverse seasonal segmentation events, including the start of navigation or the closure of winter roads, are the negotiable and flexible processes and integral parts of foodscape itself (Ibid, p. 159).

Thus, seasonality and complementarity of transport infrastructures determine the viability of local communities. On the one hand, due to the availability of transport infrastructures, transportation hubs like Egvekinot sustain the local population better than more remote villages of the Arctic region which multiple deficits have been extensively discussed in the literature (e.g. Davydov & Bobrova, 2024; Davydova & Davydov, 2022; Gavrilova & Vasilieva, 2022; Liarskaya, 2017; Vasilieva & Gavrilova, 2022). This infrastructural advantage has led to migration from surrounding areas as people seek greater stability and access to goods. On the other hand, the quality of life in Egvekinot remains subject to seasonal fluctuations; it changes significantly from abundance in October to scarcity in June. In other words, the quality of life is not stable, frozen, or prescribed to certain communities. Rather, it is a process, not an outcome, and it changes throughout the year with the seasonal fluctuations of infrastructure that predetermine the logistics of supply.

Ultimately, the case of Egvekinot highlights the interplay between infrastructure, seasonality, and human practices in shaping Arctic food security and sustainability. While the town enjoys relatively better supply than more isolated settlements, it is not immune to the cyclical disruptions inherent in the overall system of provisioning in the Russian Arctic. Thus, our research on the seasonality of the Arctic system of supply and provisioning highlights the dynamic nature of transport infrastructure contingent upon environmental, social, and political factors. It demonstrates that infrastructural connections (and disruptions) are reconfirmed by climate change, social practices, and policy regulations.

Notes

1. Ozernyi is a micro-district of Egvekinot, but located 13 km away.
2. *Sotsial'nyi magazin* is a status prescribed to a particular trading company and a form of social welfare from the local government which partly cover transportation costs of this company.
3. See more on the overdue food in Chukotka in our previous research (Davydova & Davydov, 2022).
4. TREKOL is an abbreviation for *transport ekologicheskii* (ecological transport) and is the brand-name of these all-terrain vehicles. The company's website can be found at <https://www.trecol.ru/>.
5. The war in Ukraine.

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